

INFLUENCE OF DRUG USE ON STUDENT ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN MATINYANI DISTRICT, KENYA

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to investigate the influence of drug use on student interest in learning and identify counselling interventions that can be used when dealing with drug use among secondary school students in Matinyani district. Descriptive survey was used in this study. Fourteen public secondary schools were involved with population of 1701 students. Purposive sampling was used in the sample selection to select 5 schools which included a girls' boarding, a boys' boarding school, a mixed day school, a mixed boarding school and a mixed day and a boarding school. A sample size of 269 was used. The data was collected by use of a Core Alcohol and Drug Survey Questionnaire. Validity and reliability of the study instrument was established through a pilot study. A correlation coefficient alpha of 0.7408 was obtained. According to, Fraenkel and Wallen (2002) a reliability coefficient of 0.7 or more implies high degree of reliability. Data was analysed by use of descriptive statistics with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). The descriptive analysis, percentages, tables, bar graphs and charts were used in presenting and summarizing the findings. The study established that drug use lead to increased lack interest in learning among students. The study further established that it is the responsibility of all members of society to fight drug use in our country. This is so because when students use drugs, the effects are felt all over. The study recommends that; teacher counselors should adopt group counseling and peer counseling techniques in assisting adolescents overcome the problem of drug use; schools should have active and working guidance and counseling

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departments with well trained personnel to handle drug related case; school administrators should discourage transfers/admissions of indiscipline students from one school to another; among other recommendations.

Keywords: Matinyani district, drug use, discipline and interest in learning, counselling intervention

1. Introduction

There is growing concern worldwide today over growing number of youth using drugs that the law does not permit or prohibit. The existence and extent of drug use has been identified as one of the greatest problem in learning institutions. This affects various aspects of learning such as student's discipline and interest in learning hence affecting academic performance. Drugs are chemical substances that modify mental, emotional and behavioral functioning American Psychological Association (2000).

According to the World Drug report (2005), the use of illicit drugs has increased throughout the recent years. The report further states that a major World trend is the increasing availability of many kinds of drugs. A report released by United Nations Drugs Control Programme (2004) 4.8% of the global population consume drugs, but the worrying fact is that according to, United Nations Drugs Control Programme executive director (2004) those hooked are the youth. In China, it was reported that drug use is going up while the age of new users is going down. A survey in the Czech Republic showed that 37% of new drug users were teenagers between 15- 18 years old. Drug use in particular heroine is becoming a serious problem in Egypt where around 6% of sampled secondary school students admitted to have experimented with drugs. In Pakistan, it was reported that the share of those who started using heroine at 15-20 years has doubled. Africa's role in global drug supply chain is increasing. Already the continent is second largest region for cannabis production, trafficking and consumption accounting for 26% of global Seizures of this drug in 2001 (UNODC, 2004).

In Kenya today drug use has become prevalent than at any other times (NACADA, 2010). Majority of the users are students in secondary schools, tertiary colleges and universities. They further point out that the use of the drugs has spread at a fast rate and reached every part of the country. Use of drugs can be traced back to pre-colonial days when alcohol and other drugs were used and consumed as part of traditions of the communities. The communities had virtues and values that strictly guided the use of drugs. Generally, consumption of alcohol, tobacco and other drugs was a privilege of the elders, more often than not male elders. The actual existence of

drug use as a social problem was rare because of strong social structures. The low levels or nonexistence of drug use was sustained as a result of strong kinship ties that ran through different social institutions. Traditions and taboos were upheld to discourage the misuse of drugs.

One of the most common consequences of drug use is keeping up with academic responsibilities. According to National Institute on Alcohol and Alcoholism (2005) in United State of America about 25% of student's experience difficulty in academics due to drug use. Such difficulties include earning low grades, doing poorly on test, missing class and falling behind in academic performance. Even students who don't use drugs may suffer academically as a result of their peers taking drugs. The so called secondary effects of drugs include taking care of friends on drugs and being victims of assault which can affect school work of students who don't use drug. These consequences can have dramatic results. School administration report that significant number of students who drop out of school do so because drugs interfere with their academics. Drug use undermine academic mission of schools, colleges and universities. Drug use and its effect on student's performance can lead to a decline in the overall academic performance of a school as a result schools may face declining retention rates and poor reputation. Schools with reputation of 'drug use' may attract students who engage in high-risk behaviors and may discourage prospective students who are looking for an academically vigorous institution.

One of the top schools in Kitui County, Eastern Province, of Kenya, is today a shadow of its former self. The school is now infamous for poor academic performance. According to the Principal of the institution, the declining academic performance of the school can be attributed to rampant drug use among students. In Matinyani District where rains are inconsistent and unreliable, education is a major investment that determines the livelihood of many people. Many parents have realized this and hence invest heavily on education of their children.

2. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the influence of drug use on student discipline and interest in learning and identify counselling interventions that can be used to deal with drug use among secondary school students in Matinyani district.

2.1 Objectives of the Study

The study was guided by the following objectives: -

- i. To establish whether drug use affects student interest in learning among secondary school students in Matinyani District.
- ii. To identify counseling interventions that can be put in place to deal with drug use among secondary school students in Matinyani District.

2.2 Significance of the Study

The findings may help the Ministry of Education and school administrators in the development of strategies for students' behaviour management in schools. Students may be helped by the findings of the study by being made aware of effects of drug use on academic performance and hence be more cautious and instead concentrate on studies. The study findings might help curriculum developers in formulating and incorporating psycho-education programs in secondary schools. The findings may also be useful to school's management to come up with drug policies and put in place suggested counseling interventions.

2.3 Limitations of the Study

Students may not give genuine information because of fear. This is because drug use is illegal and therefore students may fear being victimized. The other notable limitation was the generalization of the anticipated findings of the study since the study involved purposive sampling which would not allow results to be generalized to all schools, both private and public.

3. Literature Review

3.1 Influence of Drug Use on Students Interest in Learning

Drug users have decreased interest in class work and negative attitude which make them drop out of school before accomplishing their studies, Leadership (2004). Drug users have decreased interest in completion of task, decreased ability to perform task that require a lot of concentration and paying attention which interfere with learning, Leadership (2004). They are unmotivated, apathetic without goals or objectives and without wish to succeed in anything, Melgosa (1997). Students on drugs arrive to school late and lack energy.

3.2 Counselling Implication

Counselling of substance users is very vital in that professionals should give public and professional education programs. These includes presentation to different groups as such as schools, churches or media talks to bring awareness on effects of drug use on

the body and prevention measures of drug use outlined. These preventions can be done in three levels; primary prevention which is done to prevent drug use and therefore no new cases develop. Secondary prevention which aims at lowering the number of those already identified as quickly as possible and restore health back. Tertiary prevention activities to keep down total number of those already addicted and to help recover their health back to avoid relapse and maintain good health (Kinney, 2006).

Another major task of counsellor is to educate student on the nature of drug use illness, developmental stage of growth, health education and the underlying principles that may influence health habits, behaviors and causal factors of drug use.

3.3 Research Design

The research was a descriptive survey adopting *ex-post facto* research design.

3.4 Population of the Study

All 1701 students in 14 public secondary school in Matinyani District.

3.5 Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

Purposive sampling was used in selecting 5 schools out of 14 schools based on sample. Simple random sampling was used to select 269 participants from each school.

3.6 Data Analysis

The data was analysed using descriptive statistics with the aid of statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 17.0 for windows. The descriptive analysis, percentages tables, graphs and chart were used in presenting and summarizing the findings.

4. Effects of Drug Use towards Students Interest in Learning

The first objective of the study was to establish whether drug use affect student interest in learning among secondary school students in Matinyani District. Presented in Table 1 are some of the consequences of drug use.

Table 1: Consequences of Drug Use on Students Interest in Learning

Effects of drug use	Frequency	Percent
Noise making	243	90.3
Sneaking out of school	222	82.5
Lack of interest in school work	215	79.9
Truancy	189	70.2

As indicated in Table 1 majority of the students' reported that drug use leads to noisemaking (90.3%), sneaking out of school (82.5%), lack of interest in school work 79.9 %, and truancy 70.2 %. Drug and alcohol use is one of the most challenging issues in schools. This is because drug and alcohol use is linked with school unrests, lack of interest in school work and school's dropouts. According to, Kerochio (1994) the society becomes alarmed when a persons' use of drugs results in impairment of occupational or social functioning. The user becomes a threat to other members of society and engages in criminal activities. Hartmatz (1973) discovered that drugs tend to make users to have erratic mood swings, anxious and impulsive. They lead to poor social adjustment on part of the user characterized by situational hostility.

4.1 Interventions Put in Place to Curb Drug Use among Students in School

The second objective of the study was to identify interventions that can be put in place to deal with drug use among secondary school students in Matinyani District. To address this objective, students were requested to indicate measures that were used in their school to minimize drug use among students. The following table shows their responses.

Table 2: Strategies used in Schools to Curb Drug Usage

Strategies	Frequency	Percent
Offering group counselling/ health guidance	269	100.0
Creating smoke and drug free environment in learning institutions	269	100.0
Offering frequent awareness campaigns in schools e.g. teaching about NACADA	242	90.0
Referral to rehabilitation centers	220	81.8
Administration being strict in enforcing school rules and regulations	214	79.6
Strengthening peer clubs that promote life skills education in schools	196	72.9
Enhancing strict disciplinary measures e.g. expulsion of drug users	182	67.7
Discouraging transfer/admission of indiscipline students from one school to another	173	64.3
Religious leaders intensifying spiritual guidance and counseling	150	55.8

As shows in Table 2, majority of the students were of the views that to curb drug and alcohol use in schools the following strategies should be put in place: offering group counseling/health guidance (100.0%), creating smoke and drug free environment in learning institutions (100.0%), offering frequent awareness campaigns in schools e.g. NACADA (90.0%) and referral to rehabilitation centres (81.8%). In line with the above recommendations, NACADA, (2001) gave the following resolutions: Create smoke and drugs free environment in learning institutions; train Head Teachers/Education Managers on what drugs are, their effects, signs and methods to deal with them; strengthening peer clubs that promote life skills in all schools; discourage

transfers/admissions of indiscipline students from one school to another; sensitize the school communities through multi-sectoral approach on drugs and substance use and all stakeholders to shoulder the responsibility of ensuring that drug and substance use are eradicated i.e. Parents, Teachers, Churches, Non-Governmental Organizations and Government Agencies.

Dryfoos (1990) argues that the following can be helpful suggestions: Early intervention. This would work best when implemented before the onset of drug use; Counseling about drug use should be available throughout the school years. Training of effective personnel (teachers) schools should provide time and resources for in service training and supervision; social skills training especially focused on coping skills and resistance to peer pressure; and peer led programmes are often more effective than teacher led or counselor led especially when older students are the leaders and role models for younger students. Prevention of drug use in secondary schools is based on the notion that the shaping of student's behaviour is not the responsibility of the school counsellor and the principal alone but of all the members of the school community, Griffins (1994).

5. Conclusions

The study established that drug use interest in learning. The major consequences were: noisemaking (90.3%), sneaking out of school (82.5%), lack of interest in school work (79.9%) and truancy. The study therefore, concludes that its responsibility of all members of society to fight drug use in our country. This is so because when students use drugs, the effects are felt all over. Moreover, the problems indirectly touch the lives of all of us, either through the personal contact we may have with a troubled young person or indirectly, through heightened anxiety about the safety of schools and neighborhoods.

6. Recommendations

Teacher counselors should adopt group counseling and peer counseling techniques in assisting adolescents overcome the problem of drug use. Peer counselors should be engaged in orientation of new adolescents joining school at form one, in order to advise them on how to stay away from drugs. Schools should have active and working guidance and counseling departments with well trained personnel to handle drug related case.

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